

QUIZ**LAST NAME:** Sengretsi**FIRST NAME:** Lisa**PROGRAM CODE:** LLM**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit, delete text to show actual information below**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did not use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

ACA-401 QUIZ

1. **“Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.” Which of the following is an appropriate paraphrase of the quote above?**
 - The act of using a source of information that does not belong to you without duly acknowledging the author of the information source is plagiarism?¹**
 - Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.
 - Plagiarism is the act of using a source of information belonging to another writer.
 - Plagiarism is using a source of information.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 8.

2. **Which of the following can be considered one of the most important reasons for using a style guide?**
- To save the writer proofreading and correction time
 - To demonstrate the writer's ability to follow a style
 - To ensure consistency across a writer's works²**
 - To teach a writer how to use punctuation, grammar and vocabulary correctly
3. **If good writers are not born with a special writing gene, what gives them the ability to write well?**
- Good writers are actually born with a special gene meant for writing.
 - People become good writers by writing very often
 - People become good writers by practicing good writing habits like reading regularly, writing often, trying different forms of writing, becoming students of good writing, etc.³**
 - People become good writers by reading a lot of books
4. **Which of the following are characteristics of a good essay?**
- Stimulating ideas, logical organization of ideas, the writer's engaging voice, original word choice, sentences that are easy to read, correct punctuation, spelling and grammar⁴**

² Ibid., 24.

³ Dave Kemper, Verne Meyer, and Patrick Sebranek, *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning*. (Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, a Houghton Mifflin Company Wilmington, 1999), 4.

⁴ Ibid., 21-23.

- Long sentences, absence of the writer's voice, correct punctuation, spelling and grammar
 - Creative word choice, sentences that cannot be easily understood, correct punctuation, grammar and spelling
 - Stimulating ideas arranged in a haphazard manner, original word choice and sentences that are easy to understand
5. **It is important for researchers, especially those working on conceptual questions to answer the 'so what' question. Why is answering this question important?**
- It tells the reader what the research is about
 - It convinces the reader that the research report is worth reading⁵**
 - Answering the 'so what' question is actually not important
 - It shows the reader which theories the researcher agrees and disagrees with
6. **Which of the following a reason for citing your sources?**
- To give credit to the author of the source of information cited⁶**
 - To disconnect a researcher's work from the work of other researchers
 - To prevent readers from using the sources you have cited for further research
 - To allow the researcher use information from inaccurate sources

⁵ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 17.

⁶ Ibid., 86.

7. **The following are examples of irrelevant information commonly found in research papers except ...**

- Anecdotal information
- Unnecessary background
- Subjectivity and the use of superlatives
- Objectivity and the statement of accurate facts⁷**

8. **Common errors in research papers include the following except ...**

- Superficiality
- Objectivity⁸**
- Anthropomorphism
- Wrong verb tense

9. **What are the principal elements of a legal citation?**

- A signal, parenthetical information and the date
- The date, parenthetical information and the case number
- The authority or source, parenthetical information and the date
- The signal, parenthetical information and the authority or source⁹**

10. **In the instance where one authority is considered more helpful or authoritative than the other authorities cited within a signal, it is listed**

⁷ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 4*. (Washington DC: Euclid University, 2015), 5-6.

⁸ Ibid.

⁹ Columbia Law Review Association et al., *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation*, 19th ed. (Massachusetts: Harvard Law Review Association, 2010), 3.

before the other authorities. In the situation where this is not the case, authorities are listed in a particular order. Which of the following authorities comes first?

- Treaties and other international agreements
- Cases
- Statutes
- Constitutions¹⁰**

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

Columbia Law Review Association, Harvard Law Review Association, University of Pennsylvania Law Review, and The Yale Law Journal. *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation*. 19th ed. Massachusetts: Harvard Law Review Association, 2010.

EUCLID. *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 4*. Washington DC: Euclid University, 2015.

Kemper, Dave, Verne Meyer, and Patrick Sebranek. *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning*. Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, a Houghton Mifflin Company Wilmington, 1999.

Turabian, Kate. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 8th ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰ Ibid., 56-59.